

oxidation of glycoside which liberated one mole of HCO_2H with consumption of three moles of sodium metaperiodate supported the pyranose form of both the sugars. The almond enzymatic hydrolysis of the glycoside afforded **2** (m.m.p. and co-tlc), D-galactose and D-glucose (co-pc), confirming the β -linkage in both the sugars and the aglycone. This led to the formulation of new glycoside as 3,3'-di-O-methylellagic--acid-4-O- β -D-galactopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 4)- β -D-glucopyranoside. The 60 MHz $^1\text{Hnmr}$ spectra (CDCl_3) of the acetylated glycoside also supported the formulation (**1**) for glycoside, δ 4.90 (1H, d, J 7Hz, H-1''), 4.70 (1H, d, J 7Hz, H-1''), 4.00 (3H, s, $1 \times \text{OMe}$), 3.90 (3H, s, $1 \times \text{OMe}$), 7.20 (2H, s, H-5 and 5'), 2.0 (3H, s, $1 \times \text{OAc}$), 2.06 (6H, s, 2''-OAc and 3''-OAc), 2.08 (3H, s, 6''-OAc), 2.04 (6H, s, 2''-OAc and 3''-OAc), 2.02 (3H, s, 4''-OAc), 2.10 (3H, s, 6''-OAc) and 3.50–3.80 (12H, m, sugar-protons).

1; R = galactosyl-(1 \rightarrow 4)-glucoside
2; R = H

Experimental

Extraction: The air-dried and powdered stem bark (3 kg) of *D. discolor* procured from the United Chemical and Allied Product, Calcutta, was exhaustively extracted with rectified spirit under reflux for 30 days. The total spirit extract (40 dm³) was concentrated (300 ml) and poured into distilled water (1 dm³). The water-soluble fraction was concentrated to a syrupy mass and successively extracted with petroleum ether, C_6H_6 , CHCl_3 , EtOAc , Me_2CO and MeOH . The MeOH extract was passed through a column of silica gel and eluted from Me_2CO — MeOH (1 : 1). The eluate was concentrated and the product on crystallisation from MeOH — Et_2O mixture afforded brown coloured crystals of **1** (1.3 g) (Found; C, 51.39; H, 4.60. $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{30}\text{O}_{18}$ calcd for: C, 51.39; H, 4.58%). Acetylation of **1** with Ac_2O / Py gave an acetate, m.p. 180–82° (Found; C, 53.29; H, 4.60. $\text{C}_{44}\text{H}_{46}\text{O}_{20}$ calcd. for: C, 53.33; H, 4.64%).

Acid hydrolysis of the glycoside: The glycoside (800 mg) was refluxed with aqueous H_2SO_4 (7%, 40 ml) for 3 h, cooled and extracted with ether. The ether extract was evaporated and the residue crystallised (MeOH — Et_2O) to yield **2** as pale yellow crystals (lit. m.p. 274°) (Found: C, 58.12; H, 3.02; OMe, 18.75. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_8$ calcd. for: C, 58.18, H, 3.03; OMe, 18.78%). The aqueous layer after neutralisation (BaCO_3) was shown to be a mixture of D-galactose and D-glucose (co-pc).

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the Director, C.D.R.I., Lucknow, and Defence Laboratory, Gwalior, for the spectral and analytical data, and to Ms. A. Jain, Chemistry Department of this University for the authentic samples.

References

- R. N. CHOPRA, S. L. NAYAR and I. C. CHOPRA, "Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants", C.S.I.R., New Delhi, 1950, p. 163.
- K. R. KIRTIKAR and B. D. BASU, "Indian Medicinal Plants", L. M. Basu, Allahabad, 1935, Vol. 1, p. 542.
- S. K. SRIVASTAVA and S. PITRE, *Curr. Sci.*, 1985, **54**, 998.
- A. JAIN and S. K. SRIVASTAVA, *Curr. Sci.*, 1984, **53**, 1233.
- B. P. MOORE, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1964, **17**, 901.
- GREISSMEYER, *Anal. Chem.*, 1871, **51**, 160.
- S. MALHOTRA and K. MISHRA, *Phytochemistry*, 1981, **20**, 2043.
- L. R. ROW and G. S. R. S. RAO, *Tetrahedron*, 1962, **18**, 357.
- T. R. SRSHADRI and K. VASISHTA, *Phytochemistry*, 1965, **4**, 312.
- T. R. SRSHADRI and K. VASISHTA, *Phytochemistry*, 1965, **4**, 989.
- L. JURD, K. J. PALMER, F. STILT and J. N. SHOOLERY, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, **81**, 4620.
- S. HAKOMORI, *J. Biochem. Tokyo*, 1964, **55**, 205.
- O. MIKES, "Chromatographic Method", Van Nostrand, London, 1967, p. 77.
- F. LEDERER, "Chromatography", Elsevier, New York, 1967, p. 251.

Microdetermination of Phosphate with 2-Carboxy-2'-hydroxy-3',5'-dimethylazobenzene-4-sulphonic Acid

S. B. GHOLSE* and B. K. DESHMUKH

Laxminarayan Institute of Technology, Nagpur University,
Nagpur-440 010

Manuscript received 18 October 1982, revised 8 October 1986,
accepted 13 November 1986

2-CARBOXY-2'-hydroxy-3',5'-dimethylazobenzene-4-sulphonic acid (CHDMAS, $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{O}_6\text{S}$) has been described as a reagent for the spectrophotometric studies of Pd^{II} , Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} ^{1,2}, Fe^{III} and Al^{III} ³. Bokare *et al.*⁴ determined the stepwise stability constant of CHDMAS- Fe^{III} complex using a potentiometric technique. The reagent has also been employed for the determination of fluoride in water⁵. The decrease of absorbance of the Mg^{II} -CHDMAS complex on addition of phosphate at the λ_{max} has been found to be quantitative, and a method has been evolved for the determination of phosphate in trace quantities.

Experimental

Mg^{II} and phosphate solutions were prepared by dissolving magnesium sulphate (A.R.) and potassium dihydrogen orthophosphate (A.R.), respectively,

and standardised⁶. The dye CHDMAS was synthesised⁷ from 5-sulphoanthranilic acid. The acid was diazotised⁸ and immediately coupled with 2,4-dimethylphenol in alkaline medium. The product was isolated as its barium salt and converted into sodium salt by treating with a calculated amount of sodium sulphate. The sodium salt was recrystallised from aqueous ethanol. Finally, the dye was purified by making its free acid. The free acid was crystallised repeatedly from 50% ethanol. About 8.0×10^{-4} M solution of the dye was used for the spectrophotometric studies. The pH was adjusted with ammonium hydroxide (2 M) and ammonium chloride (2 M) solution.

Absorbance measurements were carried out on a Beckman DU-2 spectrophotometer with 10 mm quartz cells and pH measurements were made with a Elico LI-10 T pH meter.

Phosphate determination: An aliquot (2.0 ml) of 8.0×10^{-4} M Mg^{II} and 8.0×10^{-4} M CHDMAS (2.0 ml) and less than 50 μ g phosphate solution in 10.0 ml was adjusted to pH 11.0 with the help of ammonium hydroxide and ammonium chloride buffer. The absorbance of the solution was measured at 510 nm against the reagent blank. The decrease in absorbance (i.e. the absorbance in presence and absence of phosphate) was noted. The quantity of phosphate present was computed from the calibration curve constructed by measuring absorbance using different known amount (0–60 μ g) of phosphate.

Results and Discussion

The absorption spectra of Mg^{II} -CHDMAS-phosphate system at pH values 8.0–11.5, revealed the optimum pH for the work to be 11.0–11.5. The study of complex formation as a function of pH showed that the complex formed at pH 11.0 has a constant maximum absorbance. Equimolar amount of CHDMAS was sufficient for maximum absorption which was unchanged for 8 h. Beer's law was followed within the range 4–46 μ g phosphate per ml. The decrease in molar absorptivity of the Mg^{II} -CHDMAS complex was 7.5×10^3 , and the Sandell's sensitivity⁹ 0.16 μ g phosphate per cm^2 . pH is adjusted after the addition of CHDMAS to the Mg^{II} solution to avoid precipitation. A hundred-fold presence of chloride, bromide, iodide, sulphite, sulphate and nitrate had no effect on the estimation of phosphate.

The absorbance obtained from eight determinations of 23 μ g phosphate solution was 0.132 ± 0.005 . Relative deviation and standard deviation were found to be $\pm 2.3\%$ and $\pm 1.30\%$, respectively. The total operation required only 30 min.

References

1. O. P. SHARMA and R. B. KHARAT, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1975, 13, 848.

2. O. P. SHARMA and R. B. KHARAT, Ph.D. Thesis, Nagpur University, 1975.
3. O. P. SHARMA and R. B. KHARAT, unpublished work.
4. A. BOKAR, B. K. DESHMUKH and R. B. KHARAT, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1976, 14, 541.
5. B. K. DESHMUKH and D. S. MAHESHWARI, *Chem. Anal. (Warsaw)*, 1981, 26.
6. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", ELBS, London, 1975.
7. W. F. HARRIS and T. R. SWERT, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 77, 2893.
8. K. VENKATARAMAN, "The Chemistry of Synthetic Dyes", Academic, New York, 1952, p. 210.
9. E. B. SANDELL, "Colorimetric Determination of Traces of Metals", Interscience, New York, 1959.

Spectrophotometric Determination of Primary Aromatic Amines using Syringaldehyde

C. S. P. SASTRY, B. G. RAO and B. S. SASTRY*

Foods, Drugs and Water Analysis Branch,
Department of Chemistry, Andhra University, Waltair-530 003

Manuscript received 21 October 1982, revised 14 July 1986
accepted 26 November 1986

ALDEHYDES such as *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde¹, *p*-dimethylaminocinnamaldehyde², 2-hydroxynaphthaldehyde³, vanillin⁴, glutacetaldehyde⁵ and furfural⁶ have been utilised earlier for the spectrophotometric determination of primary aromatic amines based on the formation of coloured Schiff's bases. The stability and λ_{max} of such Schiff's bases depend upon the nature and positions of the other substituent groupings on the aromatic ring of the aldehyde moiety. In this paper, we give the results of our investigation on the utilisation of syringaldehyde (3,5-dimethoxy-4-hydroxybenzaldehyde), which has not been used earlier, for the spectrophotometric determination of primary aromatic amines including some sulpha drugs, dapsone and benzocaine.

Experimental

A 2.5% (w/v) solution of syringaldehyde (Fluka) was prepared in alcohol. Standard solutions of some sulpha drugs (sulphathiazole, sulphamethoxy pyridazine, sulphamethizole, sulphaguanidine, sulphadiazine, sulphapyridine and sulphafurazole), dapsone, benzocaine and aniline were prepared by dissolving of each compound (I.P. or B.P. grade) (50 mg) in methanol (500 ml). Tablet powder or suspension equivalent to 50 mg of each drug was extracted with methanol (3 \times 50 ml), and the combined methanolic extract was filtered and the volume made upto 500 ml with methanol.

All uv absorbance measurements were made on a Shimadzu 140 double beam spectrophotometer.

* Department of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Andhra University Waltair-530 003.